

Exploring individualized teaching strategies in vocational college students' employment courses based on MBTI personality

Wei Yin¹, Sri Suryanti^{2*} and Chomphu Kotirum³

Department of Education and Society, Institute of Science Innovation and Culture, Rajamangala University of Technology Krungthep, Thailand.

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ABSTRACT

Based on the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI), this study explored the effect of Individualized teaching strategies in vocational college students' employment courses. Given the different personality types of students, the study aims to improve students' participation, understanding, and employability in employment courses through tailored teaching methods. The study adopted a mixed research method, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews to evaluate the effectiveness of Individualized teaching compared with traditional teaching methods. The results showed that matching teaching strategies with students' MBTI personality types can improve students' learning outcomes and enhance their self-confidence and employment readiness. This study highlights the importance of Individualized education in vocational college education and teaching.

Keywords: MBTI (Myers-Briggs Type Indicator), vocational college students, employment courses, individualized teaching strategies, employability skills.

*Corresponding author. E-mail: sri.s@mail.rmutk.ac.th.

INTRODUCTION

Vocational education has an important role in preparing students to enter the world of work with skills that are in accordance with industrial needs (OECD, 2021). One of the main challenges in teaching vocational courses is the diversity of student learning styles, which are influenced by their personality characteristics (Felder and Brent, 2005). A more reliable teaching approach is increasingly important to increase the effectiveness of learning and student work readiness (Kolb, 2015). In this context, personality theory, such as the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI), can be used to develop teaching strategies more per individual learning preferences (Jung, 1921; Briggs Myers and Briggs, 1995).

Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) divides personality into four central dichotomies: Extrovert vs. Introvert, Sensing vs. Intuition, Thinking vs. Feeling, and Judging vs. Perceiving (Briggs Myers et al., 1998). Each combination of this dichotomy reflects how individuals absorb, process, and apply information. Varied personality types of students will have varied learning

styles in their education (Felder and Silverman, 1988). While some students find theoretical and reflective approaches (Kolb, 2015) more comfortable, others may be more effective in learning through direct experience and practice—experiential learning. Therefore, a teaching approach that does not consider personality differences can cause gaps in understanding and learning effectiveness (Felder and Brent, 2005).

This study conducted an empirical analysis to explore the relationship between personality types based on MBTI and the most effective teaching strategy in vocational courses focusing on student work readiness. This study aims to identify how the personalized teaching strategy can help improve students' skills and readiness in dealing with the world of work (Brown et al., 2019). The research method includes the selection of participants, personality type analysis with MBTI instruments, and applying various teaching strategies based on individual students' characteristics (Jung, 1921; Felder and Brent, 2005). The findings of this

study are expected to provide insight for educators and practitioners in designing teaching methods that are more effective and in accordance with the needs of vocational students. By implementing personality-based teaching strategies, learning in vocational tertiary institutions is expected to be more optimal in improving student competencies and readiness for entering the world of work (OECD, 2021).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) and learning preferences

One of the most widely used methods for classifying personality traits is the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI). This model is based on Carl Jung's personality theory, which was developed by Katharine C. Briggs and Isabel Briggs Myers during World War II (Quenk, 2009). Cohen et al. (2013) assert that the MBTI framework categorizes individuals into four dichotomous personality dimensions: Introversion (I) versus Extroversion (E), Sensing (S) contrasted with Intuition (N), Thinking (T) opposed to Feeling (F), and Judging (J) compared to Perceiving (P).

The MBTI framework has been extensively applied in educational environments to study student learning strategies, environmental activities, and decision-making processes. Studies reveal that various MBTI personality types have usual preferences and learning behaviors (Tzeng et al., 1989). While introverted pupils are more developed in an autonomous learning environment centered on personal pacing, extroverted students prefer interactive and cooperative learning. Students with sensation preferences tend to focus on concrete details and structured instructions, while students with intuition preferences are superior at abstract thinking and innovative problem-solving. Students with the orientation of thinking prioritize logical reasoning and objective decision-making, while students with an orientation feel more, prioritize emotional aspects and interpersonal harmony. Finally, individuals who have preferences to assess more structured learning with clear goals, whereas individuals with preferences to understand more easily adapt to flexible and spontaneous learning (Blickle, 1996).

MBTI in vocational education and employment courses

The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) framework is increasingly utilized to enhance the efficacy of tailored teaching methodologies in vocational education, especially in programs that necessitate cultivating practical skills for the labor market. Studies indicate that tailoring instructional strategies to align with students' personality types can enhance their educational outcomes and readiness for employment (Felder and

Silverman, 2002). For example, vocational students with sensation preferences benefit more from practice-based training and real-world application. In contrast, students with intuitive preferences are superior when allowed to explore theoretical concepts and innovative solutions (Kolb et al., 2001). In employment courses, students with personality type assessment (judging) tend to be superior in structured training programs with clear targets. At the same time, individuals with perceiving preferences (perceiving) prefer adaptive learning environments that encourage creativity and exploration. Understanding this difference allows educators to design learning strategies following various student learning styles, increasing their career involvement and readiness (Hawk and Shah, 2007).

Relationship between MBTI and problem-based learning in vocational education

Since problem-based learning (PBL) successfully fits the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) paradigm, it is a pedagogical approach that fits very well. Studies show that whilst more introverted people prefer solitary research and introspection, extroverted pupils flourish in settings marked by group discussions and cooperative projects (Drummond and Stoddard, 1992). Learners with sensation preferences benefit from structured case studies, while learners with more intuition preferences are involved in open projects that require creative problem-solving (Busato et al., 2000). In addition, students with a tendency to think (thinking) are superior in solving analysis and data-based problems, while students with feeling preferences (feeling) emphasize the ethical and interpersonal dimensions of the challenges of the world of work more. Students with this type of judging tend to be successful in projects with a clear deadline, while students with this type of understanding prefer a dynamic and developing project. By integrating MBTI-based insights into PBL, vocational educators can optimize student learning experiences and improve their readiness to deal with the real world of work (Myers-Briggs, 2009).

Furthermore, applying MBTI-based teaching strategies in PBL can increase the effectiveness of employment courses in vocational tertiary institutions. By understanding how students' personality affects how they absorb and apply knowledge, instructors can design more personal and adaptive learning methods. For example, students with sensation preferences and assessing can be given a structured work simulation, while students with intuition preferences and understanding can be facilitated with flexible, innovative projects. This approach increases student involvement in learning and provides them with critical thinking skills and adaptation needed in the growing world of work. Therefore, MBTI-based individual teaching strategies in PBL are effective solutions to improve student work readiness in vocational education (JingXuan, 2024).

Implementing individualized teaching strategies based on MBTI

Given the diversity of learning preferences among vocational college students, uniform teaching approaches are often less effective. Instead, the individualized teaching strategy based on the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) classification can increase student involvement and understanding. For example, educators can design a flexible curriculum by combining structured learning plans for students with the type of judgment and exploration open for students with the type of understanding (Duff et al., 2004). In addition, using a combination of practical activities for students with sensation preferences and conceptual discussions for students with intuition preferences (intuition) can increase knowledge retention and overall skills development. Interactive tools such as the Learning Management System (LMS), adaptive assessments, and career simulations can further support personalized learning experiences. By implementing MBTI-based strategies, vocational educators can create an inclusive and dynamic learning environment that accommodates the uniqueness of each student, thereby increasing their work readiness and career success (Furnham, 1992).

Furthermore, applying MBTI-based teaching strategies can also increase the effectiveness of skills training in accordance with industrial needs. Students with thinking preferences (thinking) can be encouraged to complete data-based analytical assignments. In contrast, students with feeling preferences can be given a case-based scenario emphasizing interpersonal and ethical aspects in the world of work. In addition, extroverted students can be placed in teams in project-based learning to develop communication and collaboration skills. In contrast, introverted students can be given a role that allows them to work independently and contribute to in-depth analysis. With this approach, vocational education institutions can ensure that the teaching methods applied increase the effectiveness of learning and prepare students with skills that align with the dynamic and diverse work environment.

METHOD

Literature collation method

The literature collation method systematically collects, classifies, organizes, and summarizes the literature in related fields to construct the study's theoretical foundation and background framework. This paper uses the literature collation method to comprehensively collect and classify the existing literature on MBTI personality theory, Individualized teaching strategies, career development theory, and employment curriculum reform. In the process of collation, the methods of econometric analysis and content classification were used to filter and screen a large amount of literature to ensure the relevance and authority of the selected literature. By

sorting this literature systematically, this paper clarifies the main direction and focus of the research. It provides solid theoretical support and a reference basis for the subsequent empirical analysis.

Questionnaire survey method

The questionnaire survey method is a quantitative research method that obtains research data and information by compiling a series of questions and then distributing them in written form to the respondents and collecting, counting, and analyzing their responses. The questionnaire method is suitable for collecting a large amount of structured data, can quickly and economically collect a large amount of data, and at the same time can provide the researcher with objective data analysis results. The questionnaire for this study is designed in three parts to specifically analyze the satisfaction of the different personalities of the students under study with the individualized teaching methods, and to propose targeted teaching strategies. In the third part of the questionnaire, this paper introduces a Likert 5-point scale assessment method to allow respondents to rate the relevant questions and provide data support for subsequent research.

Mathematical statistics

The mathematical statistics method processes the collected data or information through mathematical statistics, analysis, and other ways to conclude after each data statistic and difference analysis. Mathematical statistics can be used to test the collected data to ensure its consistency and reliability. In this paper, after reading the literature to sort out the mature questionnaire developed by previous scholars (the second part of the questionnaire) and organizing the scale designed by various teachers of the college according to the research purpose of this paper (the third part of the questionnaire), combined with China's national conditions, the questionnaire suitable for this paper was finally formulated, and accurate and effective information was obtained through the questionnaire filled in by the students of C College of Yunnan Province. Excel sheets were entered to ensure the accuracy of the data. After carefully checking and comparing the raw data and confirming that there was no error, the data were analyzed empirically using SPSS 27.0 software.

The samples were selected from students of different majors from freshman to junior year in Yunnan C College, 350 questionnaires were randomly selected and distributed in September-October 2024, and 312 valid questionnaires were recovered by excluding invalid questionnaires. Moreover, the research design involved three components. The first part is the basic information, which is used for the statistics of students' names, gender, grades, and major information, totalling 4 question items. The second part is the MBTI personality

test, which measures the statistics of students with different personalities. It was written by American psychologist Katherine Cook Briggs (1875-1968) and her psychologist daughter, Isabel Briggs Myers, based on the theory of psychological types of the famous Swiss psychoanalyst Carl G. Jung and their long-term observation and research on the differences of human personality. After more than 50 years of research and development, the MBTI has become the most famous and authoritative personality test in the world today. There are 93 items in total. The third part is a Likert 5-level scale designed by various college faculty members according to this paper's research purpose for the satisfaction of Individualized teaching methods versus traditional teaching methods, a statistical analysis of two dimensions, with a total of 8 items.

SPSS 27.0 statistical software will be used to analyze the data in this study. The analysis process includes reliability and validity analysis, descriptive statistics, and analysis of variance. The survey sample of this study has passed the reliability and validity tests for the 2 variables,

1-8 question items, proving their reliability and validity for subsequent research analysis.

FINDINGS

Analysis of current situation

In this study, the satisfaction statistics of the personality, Individualized teaching methods, and traditional teaching methods of the students in Yunnan C College are as follows.

Personality statistics

(1) Based on the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI), the personality traits are divided into four dimensions, each containing two tendencies, each with a total of eight, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Statistics on the number of people with 8 kinds of tendencies.

Orientations	Number of people	Percentage (%)	Orientations	Number of people	Percentage (%)
Introversion (I)	174	55.77	Extroversion (E)	138	44.23
Sensing (S)	180	57.69	Intuition (N)	132	42.31
Thinking (T)	178	57.05	Feeling (F)	134	42.95
Judging (J)	169	54.17	Perceiving (P)	143	45.83

As shown in Table 1, by organizing and analyzing the data, there is a certain difference in the proportion of the number of people with two-level tendencies in the four dimensions, in which the proportion of students who prefer I, S, T, J is higher, which indicates that when exposed to information, introversion (I) is absorbing and digesting external information through thinking and introspection; practicality (S) prefers to pay attention to the facts and details (S); thinking (T) prefers to arrive at a reasonable through logical analysis of the results and decisions; and Judgment (J) has a preference for life and doing things according to a plan and in a well-organized manner. From the distribution of the dimensions, it is inferred that the typical MBTI type among school college students would be the ISTJ Logical Meticulous type, which is very organized and task-centred in everything; they want to concentrate on their work, and they tend to grow to be experts in a particular area by using established rules and processes carefully and precisely to complete their tasks effectively.

(2) This study statistically analyzed the number of 16 personality types among college students, and the results are shown in Figure 1.

As shown in Figure 1, the ISTJ (Introvert, Situational, Thinking, Judging) and ESTJ (Extravert, Situational,

Thinking, Judging) categories accounted for the highest percentage of the population, with the number of ISTJ personalities at 44, or 14.10% of the total, and the number of ESTJ personalities at 35, or 11.22% of the total. This shows that most university students have the personality tendency to be practical, thinking, and judging. ENFJ (Extraversion, Intuition, Emotion, and Judgment) personality has 7 people, which is the lowest percentage, accounting for only 2.24%. According to the results of the study, it can be seen that the personality types of college students generally tend to be ISTJ and ESTJ, which is consistent with the results of Wu Yuhui's study.

(3) Through MBTI personality statistics, college students can find out their personality strengths and advantages, which can help them build up self-confidence in the job-seeking process and make better use of their strengths in their future careers. Teachers can also discover their deficiencies and problems through MBTI personality statistics and should provide them with more suggestions. Individualized teaching methods develop students' inner potential and promote their all-around development, thus improving their employment competitiveness.

Figure 1. Statistical chart of the number of people with 16 personality types.

In order to better help college students apply this personality assessment tool, the 16 personality types can be divided into 8 occupational personalities (Wang, 2014), as shown in Table 2, based on the common characteristics shared by the two personality types. Then, the characteristics and strengths of each combination type are analyzed one by one, and corresponding

suggestions are made for students' career planning and employment competitiveness. Each student can make better use of his or her strengths against this result and have himself or herself cultivated and trained in the weaker areas according to the suggestions made in the Individualized teaching carried out by the college to promote his or her all-around development.

Table 2. Statistical table of 8 occupational personality divisions.

Professional personality	Personality type	Number of people	Percentage (%)
Sophisticate	ISTJ	66	21.15
	ISFJ		
Adamant	ESTJ	50	16.03
	ENTJ		
Analytical	ISTP	45	14.42
	INTP		
Explorer	ENFP	37	11.86
	ENTP		
Caring	ISFP	33	10.58
	INFP		
Visionary	INTJ	30	9.62
	INFJ		
Reactive	ESFP	28	8.97
	ESTP		
Contributor	ESFJ	23	7.37
	ENFJ		

Satisfaction statistics of individualized teaching methods and traditional teaching methods

(1) This study is divided into two dimensions: satisfaction with individualized and traditional teaching methods in improving students' learning interests, cultivating students' career planning, and enhancing students' employment prospects. The third part of the questionnaire has 8 questions: 1-4 questions for the

satisfaction survey of Individualized teaching methods and 5-8 questions for the satisfaction survey of traditional teaching methods. A 5-point Likert scale was used, with 1-5 points, "very dissatisfied" as 1 point, "dissatisfied" as 2 points, "average" as 3 points, "satisfied" as 3 points, and "very satisfied" as 3 points. "Satisfactory" is 4, and 'Very Satisfactory' is 5. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Satisfaction statistics of individualized teaching methods and traditional teaching methods.

Dimensionality	Item	N	Minimum value	Maximum values	M ± SD
Individualized teaching methods	Question 1	312	2	5	3.93 ± 0.807
	Question 2	312	2	5	3.99 ± 0.777
	Question 3	312	2	5	3.86 ± 0.820
	Question 4	312	2	5	4.02 ± 0.843
Traditional teaching methods	Question 5	312	2	5	3.06 ± 0.852
	Question 6	312	1	5	2.90 ± 0.936
	Question 7	312	1	5	2.87 ± 0.973
	Question 8	312	1	5	2.85 ± 0.963

As shown in Table 3, Yunnan C College students' satisfaction ratings of the two teaching methods, Individualized teaching method ratings, are significantly higher than traditional teaching method ratings. It can be seen that students believe that it is significantly helpful to improve learning interest, cultivate career planning, and enhance employment prospects.

(2) The number, percentage, mean, and standard deviation of students who rated more than 3 points in the two dimensions of satisfaction with Individualized and traditional teaching methods were statistically used to derive students' recognition and satisfaction with the two methods.

Table 4. Statistical table of satisfaction greater than 3 points.

Dimensionality	Greater than 3 points	Percentage (%)	M ± SD
Individualized teaching methods	265	84.94	3.95 ± 0.728
Traditional teaching methods	126	40.38	2.92 ± 0.860

As shown in Table 4, 265 students who studied at Yunnan C College rated the Individualized teaching methods greater than 3, accounting for 84.94% of the total number of students, and the average of 312 students' ratings was 3.95. It fully proves the importance of Individualized teaching methods.

Analysis of differences

The above analysis fully proves the students' recognition and satisfaction with personalized teaching methods and supports the importance and necessity of personalized teaching methods. In this study, the difference in the analysis of students' recognition and satisfaction with personalized teaching methods by gender, grade, major, and 16 personality types showed no significant difference.

Individualized teaching strategies for different occupational personalities

In this study, the 16 personality types were divided into 8 occupational personalities to cultivate students' career planning, improve their competitiveness in employment, and provide guidance and training for students' disadvantages to promote their overall development. Individualized teaching strategies are suggested for different career personalities one by one.

Thoughtful people

Meticulous people include both ISTJ and ISFJ personality types. They pay attention to details, pay attention to effectiveness, and think things through; they have a strong sense of responsibility and can

concentrate on doing one thing wholeheartedly; they like to collect and identify information, then integrate and understand this information with experience and knowledge, and use it as the primary basis for decision-making and action.

Two teaching strategies are suggested for meticulous types of individualized instruction:

(1) Be comfortable with change and uncertainty; meticulous types prefer stability and gradual progress; they are keen to maintain the status quo. However, the world is constantly changing, and there are times when meticulous people may benefit if they are willing to take risks or try novel ways of doing things. Therefore, we recommend that the meticulous person develop a sense of adaptability and flexibility to better cope with change and uncertainty.

(2) Seize the moment. The meticulous person is a dedicated person who always puts work before play, is very demanding, and has a sense of responsibility, which can sometimes cause them to neglect their physical limits, affecting their physical condition. Therefore, we suggest that meticulous people can leave some free time and extra energy to enjoy the here and now and relax at the right time.

Decisive people

Decisive people include both ESTJ and ENTJ personality types. They have a sense of responsibility, adhere to principles, and focus on work efficiency and orderly management; they have unique situational judgment and the ability to identify problems and strong organizational skills; they are good at locating the cause-and-effect relationship between things and making a quick analysis of things, to come to a conclusion and the best course of action, and act immediately.

Two teaching strategies are proposed for decisive people in Individualized teaching:

(1) Open-minded, decisive people are always eager to get started on a task; sometimes, they may make up their minds before considering all the courses of action, which often leads to bad results. Therefore, we suggest that decisive people reflect and gather more information before taking action, broaden their minds, and think deeply before making a decision.

(2) Incorporate a values-based approach to decision-making. Decisive people rely too much on logic and objectivity, and this over-reliance can prevent them from receiving and utilizing valuable information when dealing with problems, and therefore ignoring the impact of their decisions on those around them. Therefore, we suggest that decisive people consider and recognize both subjective and human factors in their decision-making process and incorporate personal values and environmental factors into their logical thinking, allowing students to be more thoughtful.

The analytical person

Analytical people include both ISTP and INTP personality types. They are good at logical analysis, concentration, and self-examination and prefer to work independently and autonomously; for analytical people, logical analysis is their nature, and when faced with problems and tasks, their first reaction is often to think logically through the information they have gathered and to keep asking questions in order to find the best course of action.

In individualized instruction, teaching strategies for analytical people: connecting with others and creating a harmonious atmosphere. Analytical people are overly objective and unsympathetic when communicating with others, and this logical and analytical approach can be perceived as cold and unsympathetic. Therefore, it is recommended that Analytical people build relationships with others and create a harmonious atmosphere.

Exploratory people

Exploratory people include both ENFP and ENTP personality types. They are passionate, energetic, responsive, and able to observe changes and ways to improve things keenly; they have strong creative thinking, like to innovate and seek development amid change; they are good at communicating and exchanging ideas, and play the role of a catalyst in the crowd.

Instructional strategies for exploratory individuals in individualized instruction: implementing career planning. Explorers are often inspired by inspiration, quickly become bored and disengaged, and lack a persistent mindset. Therefore, we recommend that explorers be persistent and implement their career plans after they are finalized.

Caring people

Caring people include both ISFP and INFP personality types. They play the role of relationship lubricant in their lives; they are warm-hearted and concerned about others, value personal values, and emphasize the harmony between their values and those of those important to them; they express themselves well, respect and appreciate others, and like to be flexible in their approach.

Two teaching strategies are suggested for the caring type in individualized instruction:

(1) Focus on rational analysis. Values-based decision-making can be one-sided if it is not balanced by rational analysis. Therefore, we recommend that caregivers focus on rational analysis as much as possible when making decisions.

(2) Avoid being overly subjective and emotional. Caregivers are always too emotionally invested in the world around them. If someone criticizes or rejects their

work, they feel the other person has hurt and offended them. It is usually tough for them to listen to others' opinions objectively. Therefore, we recommend that the caring type avoid being too subjective and emotional when dealing with problems.

Visionaries

The Visionary includes both INTJ and INFJ personality types. They like to learn and apply new knowledge in practice and are also good at reflecting on the existing knowledge they have acquired; visionaries are good at self-motivation, often show energy and integrity, and like to make detailed and complex action plans.

Instructional strategies for visionaries in individualized instruction: flexibility in planning. Visionaries like to make detailed and complex plans of action, which is originally their advantage, but once they have made a plan, it is difficult for them to change their plan of action. They are not good at being flexible in front of concrete things. Therefore, we recommend that Visionaries be flexible in implementing their plans.

Reactive people

Reactive people include both ESPP and ESTP personality types. With keen observation and rapid reaction ability, they can effectively solve unexpected situations; they have strong adaptability and high flexibility and are keen to identify changes and make positive responses proactively; they focus on practical problem-solving ability and pursue practical solutions.

Teaching Strategies for Reactive People in Individualized Instruction: Envisioning the Future. Reactive people are good at developing their practical skills or seizing opportunities to try new experiences for career advancement. However, many Reactive people do not actively envision themselves in the next few years and do not have a long-term vision. Therefore, we recommend that reactive people envision the future and use their adaptability to find the best direction for their future careers.

Contributing people

Contributing people include both ESFJ and ENFJ personality types. Contributing people are eager to pursue their ideals, loyal, and willing to give. They are always concerned about and promote harmonious social relationships; they are eager to cooperate and communicate with others, provide necessary help to others, and focus on building and maintaining good interpersonal relationships.

Teaching Strategies for Contributing People in Individualized Instruction: Focus on logic when making decisions. Considering individual needs and situations when making decisions is a strength of the contributing

person. However, there is also a need to take a logical approach to decision-making, considering your decisions' impact and consequences, which is important when planning your career path. Therefore, we recommend that contributing people focus on logic when making decisions and balance the relationship between emotions and objective factors.

DISCUSSION

This study's results show that university students' personality types generally tend to be ISTJ and ESTJ. The 16 personality types are divided into 8 combinations based on the statistical results. Then, each career personality type's characteristics and strengths are analyzed individually, and corresponding suggestions are made for career planning and life development. Students can better utilize their strengths according to the results and, at the same time, enhance their self-confidence in job hunting. According to the suggestions made in the individualized teaching carried out by the college, they can cultivate and train themselves in the weaker areas to promote their all-around development, to ultimately achieve the purpose of improving the competitiveness of employment.

Conclusion

By exploring the application of MBTI personality types and individualized teaching strategies in the employment courses of vocational colleges and universities, this study aims to reveal the role of individualized teaching in enhancing students' employment preparation, career planning, and vocational ability, and to compare the effects of individualized teaching with traditional teaching methods. Through questionnaire survey and data analysis of students in Yunnan C College, this study draws the following main conclusions: Individualized teaching methods significantly enhance students' job preparation and career planning abilities, Students' satisfaction with Individualized teaching methods is higher and significantly better than traditional teaching methods, Individualized teaching significantly improves students' employability and career competitiveness, Individualized teaching methods are outstanding in improving students' academic performance, vocational skills and teamwork, The reform of employment courses in vocational colleges and universities should pay attention to the application of Individualized teaching methods.

This study examines the effects of individualized teaching strategies based on MBTI personality types on the learning outcomes of vocational college students in employment courses, aiming to provide more customized teaching programs to improve students' employability, career planning, and learning outcomes by analyzing students' personality differences. Through the questionnaire survey and data analysis of students

in Yunnan C College, the study concluded that individualized instruction significantly improves students' engagement, employment preparation, and career planning.

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